

Synthesis of 2,2-Dimethylpyranocoumestan Derivatives

R. R. SHAH and K. N. TRIVEDI

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, M.S. University of Baroda, Baroda 390 002.

Manuscript received 22 March 1978, revised 22 April 1979, accepted 6 October 1979

6-Acetyl-2, 2-dimethyl-5-hydroxy-3, 4-dihydrochromene, 6-acetyl-2, 2-dimethyl-7-hydroxy-3, 4-dihydrochromene and 6-acetyl-7-hydroxy-2, 2, 8-trimethyl-3, 4-dihydrochromene on condensation with diethyl carbonate in presence of sodium gave 2, 2-dimethyl-3, 4-dihydro-8-hydroxy-6-oxo-6H-pyrano (2, 3-h) benzopyran, 2, 2-dimethyl-3, 4-dihydro-6-hydroxy-8-oxo-8H-pyrano (3, 2-g) benzopyran and 3, 4-dihydro-6-hydroxy-8-oxo-8H-2, 2, 10-trimethylpyrano (3, 2-g) benzopyran respectively. These on oxidative coupling with catechol in presence of potassium iodate gave the corresponding 8, 9-dihydroxy-2, 2-dimethyl-3, 4-dihydropyranocoumestan derivatives. The dimethyl ethers of these compounds could not be dehydrogenated by usual methods to the corresponding pyranocoumestan derivatives which were synthesized by the above series of reactions on the chromene derivatives obtained by prior dehydrogenation of their 3, 4-dihydro-analogues.

THE synthesis of isopsoralidine—a dihydropyranocoumestan derivative has been reported by several workers¹⁻³. In continuation of our earlier work on coumestan derivatives^{4,5}, we report here the synthesis of some pyranocoumestan derivatives.

6-Acetyl-2, 2-dimethyl-5-hydroxy-3, 4-dihydrochromene (Ia), prepared according to the method of Seshadri et al.^{6,7} by the prenylation of resacetophenone with 2-methyl-but-3-en-2-ol and BF₃-etherate, was condensed with diethyl carbonate in presence of pulverised sodium to give 2,2-dimethyl-3,4-dihydro-8-hydroxy-6-oxo-6H-pyrano(2,3-h) benzopyran(IIa) according to Boyd and Robertson⁸. This was oxidatively coupled with catechol⁹ in presence of potassium iodate and sodium acetate in aqueous acetone to give 8,9-dihydroxy-2,2-dimethyl-3,4-dihydropyrano (2,3-h)-coumestan (IIIa) which was directly methylated to 8,9-dimethoxy-2,2-dimethyl-3,4-dihydropyrano (2,3-h) coumestan (IIIb). As (IIIb) failed to undergo dehydrogenation with DDQ or palladised charcoal (10%), the synthesis of 8,9-dimethoxy-2,2-dimethylpyrano (2,3-h)-coumestan (IIIc) was finally achieved by first carrying out the dehydrogenation of 6-acetyl-2,2-dimethyl-5-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrochromene (Ia) to 6-acetyl-2,2-dimethyl-5-hydroxychromene (Id) by DDQ and subjecting the latter to the above series of reactions. The structure of 8,9-dimethoxy-2,2-dimethylpyrano (2,3-h) coumestan (IIIc) was confirmed by its NMR spectrum in CDCl₃ which showed the signals at δ 1.50 (6H, s, geminal dimethyl group at 2); 3.99 and 4.03 (each 3H, s, 2x-OCH₃ groups at 8 and 9); 5.80 and 6.85 (2d, J=9Hz, 2H at 3 and 4) and 7.00-7.85 (m,4H, aromatic protons at 7,10, 12 and 13). The IR spectrum in nujol showed the bands at 1700 cm⁻¹ (>C=O stretching), 1365 cm⁻¹ (gem.

 group), 1280 cm⁻¹ aromatic C-O-C stretching) and 3400 cm⁻¹ (H₂O). A similar synthesis of 8,9-dimethoxy-2, 2-dimethyl-3, 4-dihydroxyprano (3,2-g)

- a : 3,4-Dihydro, R₁=OH, R₂=COMe, R₃=R₄=H
 b : 3,4-Dihydro, R₁=R₄=H, R₂=COMe, R₃=OH
 c : 3,4-Dihydro, R₁=H, R₂=COMe, R₃=OH, R₄=Me
 d : 3,4-Dehydro, R₁=OH, R₂=COMe, R₃=R₄=H
 e : 3,4-Dehydro, R₁=R₄=H, R₂=COMe, R₃=OH
 f : 3,4-Dehydro, R₁=H, R₂=COMe, R₃=OH, R₄=Me

- a : 3,4-Dihydro
 b : 3,4-Dehydro

- a : 3,4-Dihydro, R=H
 b : 3,4-Dihydro, R=Me
 c : 3,4-Dehydro, R=H
 d : 3,4-Dehydro, R=Me

IV

- a : 3,4-Dihydro, R=R'=H
- b : 3,4-Dihydro, R=H, R'=Me
- c : 3,4-Dihydro, R=Me, R'=H
- d : 3,4-Dihydro, R=R'=Me
- e : 3,4-Dehydro, R=R'=H
- f : 3,4-Dehydro, R=H, R'=Me
- g : 3,4-Dehydro, R=Me, R'=H
- h : 3,4-Dehydro, R=R'=Me

V

- a : 3,4-Dihydro, R=H
- b : 3,4-Dihydro, R=Me
- c : 3,4-Dehydro, R=H
- d : 3,4-Dehydro, R=Me

VI

- a : R=H
- b : R=CH₂CH=C<Me/Me

coumestan (IVb) was achieved from 3,4-dihydro-6-acetyl-7-hydroxy-2,2-dimethylchromene (Ib), which could not be dehydrogenated to 8,9-dimethoxy-2,2-dimethylpyrano-(3,2-g) coumestan (IVf) by palladised charcoal (10%) or DDQ. (IVf) was finally synthesised from 2,2-dimethyl-6-acetyl-7-hydroxychromene (Ie) by carrying out the above series of reactions. The IR spectrum in nujol showed the bands at 1740 cm⁻¹ (>C=O group)

and 1355 cm⁻¹ (gem >C<CH₃/CH₃ group).

The synthesis of 8,9-dimethoxy-2,2,13-trimethylpyrano-(3,2-g) coumestan (IVh) was achieved by first prenylating 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methylacetophenone (VIa) with 2-methyl-but-en-2-ol and the resultant 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methyl-5-prenylacetophenone (VIb) was cyclised by DDQ to obtain 6-acetyl-7-hydroxy-2,2,8-trimethylchromene (If) which was subsequently allowed to undergo the above series of reactions to give the cou-

mestan derivative. The structure of 8,9-dimethoxy-2,2,13-trimethyl pyrano (3,2-g) coumestan (IVh) was confirmed by its NMR spectrum in CDCl₃, which showed

the bands at δ 1.50 ; (6H, s, >C<CH₃/CH₃); 2.35 (3H, s, -CH₃ at 13); 3.92 and 3.98 (each 3H, s, 2x -OCH₃ at 8 and 9), 5.70 and 6.40 (each 2H, d, J=9Hz, C-3H and C-4H) and 7.0-7.80 (3H, m, aromatic protons at 5,7 and 10).

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken in nujol on Beckman IR-20 spectrometer. NMR spectra were taken on Perkin-Elmer R-32 90 MHz spectrometer.

General procedure for the synthesis of hydroxycoumarin derivatives (IIa, IIb, Va, Vb, Vc, Vd).

A mixture of 3, 4-dihydro-2, 2-dimethyl-6-acetyl-7-hydroxychromene derivative or 2,2-dimethyl-6-acetyl-7-hydroxychromene derivative (2.0 g), diethyl carbonate (10 ml) and pulverised sodium (2.0 g) was heated on a water bath for 16 hr. After completion of the reaction, alcohol (10 ml) was added to decompose the unreacted sodium and then the mixture was added to ice-cold water. The solution was then extracted with ether to remove unreacted diethyl carbonate and the alkaline solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid. The solid was further dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and filtered. The solution on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave corresponding hydroxycoumarin derivatives (Table 1).

Methoxy derivatives of coumarins were prepared by refluxing them with dimethyl sulphate in acetone in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate.

8,9-Dihydroxy coumestan derivatives (IIIa, IIIc, IVa, IVc, IVe, IVg).

Catechol (0.01 mole) was added to a solution of hydroxy coumarin derivative (0.01 mole) and sodium acetate (0.03 mole) in (1:1) aqueous acetone (25 ml). To this, aqueous solution of potassium iodate (0.03 mole) and sodium acetate (0.03 mole) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The stirring was continued for 15 min. and the solid separated was filtered, washed with water and dried. All the coumestan derivatives showed green coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. M.ps. were above 300° and were difficult to crystallise from any organic solvent. These coumestan derivatives were directly methylated to their methyl ethers by using dimethyl sulphate in acetone (Table 2).

2,4-Dihydroxy-3-methyl-5-prenylacetophenone (VIb) :

To a stirred solution 2, 4-dihydroxy-3-methylacetophenone (1.2 g) in dry dioxan (10 ml) was added to a solution of 2-methyl-but-3-en-2-ol (0.6g) in dioxan (5ml) in presence of BF₃-etherate (0.5 ml) and the whole solution was stirred for 1 hr. at room temperature. The solution was then diluted with ether and the ether layer

TABLE 1

Coumarin derivatives	Crystallising solvent	Molecular formula	M. P.	Analysis			
				Found C	Found H	Required C	Required H
1. IIa	Aqueous alcohol	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ .H ₂ O	172°	64.21	5.72	63.63	6.06
2. Methyl ether of IIb	Benzene-Petroleum ether	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄	150°	69.85	5.26	69.77	6.42
3. Va	Aqueous alcohol	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ .H ₂ O	138°	64.55	5.79	63.63	5.06
4. Methyl ether of Va	Benzene-Petroleum ether	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄	218-20°	68.74	5.93	69.23	6.15
5. Methyl ether of Vc	Benzene-Petroleum ether	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄	185°	69.49	5.88	69.77	5.42
6. Vb	Aqueous alcohol	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄	191-93°	—	—	—	—
7. Methyl ether of Vb	Benzene-Petroleum ether	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄	178-80°	70.45	6.67	70.07	6.56
8. Vd	Aqueous alcohol	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄	210-12°	—	—	—	—
9. Methyl ether of Vd	Benzene-Petroleum ether	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄	174-76°	71.04	5.69	70.58	5.88

TABLE 2

Coumestan derivatives	Crystallising solvent	Molecular Formula	M.P.	Analysis %			
				Found C	Found H	Required C	Required H
1. IIIb	Benzene-Petroleum ether	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆	207-08°	68.99	5.21	69.47	5.26
*2. IIId	Benzene-Petroleum ether	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₆ .1/2H ₂ O	214°	67.95	4.79	68.24	4.94
3. IVb	Benzene-Petroleum ether	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆	234-35°	69.71	5.45	69.47	5.26
*4. IVf	Benzene-Petroleum ether	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₆ .1/2H ₂ O	140-42°	68.64	5.33	68.24	4.95
5. IVd	Benzene-Petroleum ether	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆	232-33°	69.72	5.97	70.07	5.58
*6. IVh	Benzene-Petroleum ether	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆ .1/2H ₂ O	220-22°	68.66	5.07	68.82	5.27

* These compounds were analysed after drying under vacuum at 120° for 20 hr.

was washed with water (3x100 ml) to discharge the colour. The solution was then washed with sodium carbonate solution (10%; 2x100 ml) which on acidification gave unreacted 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methylacetophenone (0.5 g). The etheral solution on examination by TLC (chloroform) showed the presence of two compounds. This was then subjected to column chromatography over silica gel and the column was successively eluted with (i) benzene-petroleum ether (80:20) and (ii) benzene-ethyl acetate (80:20). Fraction (i) gave a solid 2, 4 - dihydroxy- 3 -methyl- 5 -prenylacetophenone (0.4 g), crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 117-18°, (Found: C, 70.89; H, 7.45. C₁₄H₁₆O₃ requires C, 70.59; H, 7.56%); ν_{max} 3280 (OH group); 1630 (C=O) 1350 (gem. >C(CH₃)₂) cm⁻¹ NMR (CCl₄): δ 1.80, 1.82 (each 3H, s, -C(CH₃)₂); 2.10 (3H, s, -COCH₃); 2.52 (3H, s, -CH₃ at C-3; 3.30 (2H, d, J=7Hz Ar-CH₂CH=C); 5.30 (1H, t, J=7Hz >C-CH-CH₂); (1H, s, -OH) and 7.25 (1H, s, C-6H). Fraction (ii) gave the original ketone,

3,4-Dihydro-2, 2, 8-trimethyl-7-hydroxy-6-acetylchromene (Ic):

2,4-Dihydroxy-3-methyl-5-prenylacetophenone (1.0 g) was heated on a steam bath with formic acid (10 ml) for 1 1/2 hr. The solution was then poured into cold water and the solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from petroleum ether (yield 0.8 g), m. p. 112°, (Found: C, 70.80; H, 7.64) [C₁₄H₁₆O₃ requires C, 70.59; H, 7.56%]. ν_{max} 3600 (OH), 1730 (>C=O) and 1370 (>C(CH₃)₂) cm⁻¹; NMR (CCl₄): δ 1.35 (6H, s, 2-CH₃ at 2); 2.00 (3H, s, -COCH₃), 2.45 (3H, s, C-8-CH₃); 1.80, 2.73 (each 2H, t, J=8Hz, -C-CH₂-CH₂-Ar) and 7.20 (1H, s, C-5H).

2,2,8-Trimethyl-7-hydroxy-6-acetylchromene (If):

2,4-Dihydroxy-3-methyl-5-prenylacetophenone (0.2 g) was refluxed with DDQ (0.2 g) in dry benzene (10 ml) for 15 min. The solid hydroquinone separated was filtered hot and the filtrate was concentrated and the

residue was chromatographed over silica gel. The column was eluted with benzene. The solid crystallised from petroleum ether, (yield 0.1 g) m.p. 81°, (Found : C, 72.32; H, 6.68. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 72.41; H, 6.89%); ν_{max} 3200 (-OH), 1630 (>C=O), 1370 (>C(CH₃)₂) cm^{-1} ; NMR (CCl₄); δ 1.42 (6H, s, >C(Me)₂); 2.20 (3H, s, -COCH₃); 2.48 (3H, s, C-8-Me); 5.50, 6.24 (each 2H, d, J=9Hz, C-3H and C-4H) and 7.10 (1H, s, C-5H).

Acknowledgement

Authors thank Dr. Sukh Dev, Director, Multi-Chem Research Centre, Nandesari, Baroda for NMR Spectra and Dr. S. S. Lele for the microanalysis of the compounds.

References

1. D. NASIPURI and G. PYNE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 3105.
2. E. M. BICKOFF, R. L. LYMANN, A. LIVINGSTON and A. N. BOOTH, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1960, 88, 262; *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, 54, 21496f.
3. J. N. CHATTERJEA, K. D. BANERJI and N. PRASAD, *Chem. Ber.*, 1963, 98, 2358; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 59, 12774.
4. V. N. DHOLAKIA and K. N. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 351.
5. K. R. SHAH and K. N. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 224.
6. A. C. JAIN, P. LAL and T. R. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 1072.
7. A. C. JAIN, V. K. KHANNA and T. R. SESHADRI, *Tetrahedron.*, 1969, 25, 2787.
8. J. BOYD and A. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 174.
9. H. WANZLICK, R. GRITZKY and H. HEIDPREIM, *Chem. Ber.*, 1963, 96, 305; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 58, 11316h.